

SQLiteBuilder an Interactive Object/Relational Mapping (ORM) for Android Developer

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Abstract—The article presents SQLiteBuilder, an Open-Source Android ORM that restores the fun factor to SQLite Database programming. It saves development time and relieves developers of Low-Level Database requirements. An excellent relational database that is incorporated is SQLite. Nonetheless, creating SQL and analyzing query results are time-consuming and laborious jobs. [1] SQLiteBuilder removes these constraints by translating Java objects to database tables. With a basic Object-Oriented API, users can save, update, remove, and query Java objects. The SQLiteBuilder package makes it easier to create Android applications that connect with databases. An open-source, free tool for object relational mapping is called SQLiteBuilder. Data creation, updating, and access are all facilitated by ORM tools. It is a method used in programming to link an object to database data. [2]

Index Terms—SQLiteBuilder, SQLite Databases, Android, Object/Relational Mapped Tool (ORM), Java Objects, Open-Source

I. INTRODUCTION

This project created SQLiteBuilder, an Android Interactive Object/Relational Mapping (ORM). An open-source Android Object/Relational Mapped called SQLiteBuilder restores the fun of creating SQLite databases. It saves development time and relieves developers of low-level database requirements. An excellent integrated relational database is SQLite. However, writing SQL and deciphering query output are tedious and time-consuming tasks. By using a technique called object/relational mapping, or ORM, to map Java objects to database tables, SQLiteBuilder releases user from these limitations. This manner, user may use a simple object-oriented API to save, update, remove, and query Java objects. The SQLiteBuilder package makes it easier to create Android applications that connect with databases. An open-source, free tool for object-relational mapping is called SQLiteBuilder. Data creation, editing, and

access are made easier with the help of an ORM tool for Android. It's a SQLiteBuilder programming technique that associates an object with database data.[1][2][3]

II. IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODOLOGY

A. System Design: SQLiteBuilder Object Relational Mapping Framework

The SQLiteBuilder Java Android Library makes creating Android applications that communicate with SQLite persistence databases easier. An open-source, lightweight ORM (Object Relational Mapping) framework is called SQLite-Builder. Data generation, data modification, and data access are made easier using a SQLiteBuilder tool. It is a method of programming that associates an object with database data[4].

B. Existing System

The existing database connections work with the database API provided by Android SDK. Actually it is complicated to implement and need to write lots of boilerplate code.

C. Open Database Connection

To establish a database, simply use this method: open or create a database, passing in the name and mode of database connection as parameters. It gives back an instance of a SQLite database that user need to import into connection object. The syntax is shown below.

```
SQLite db = CreateDatabase( "database name", MODE_PRIVATE, null);
```

D. Create Table

The SQLiteDatabase class's execSQL function allows us to construct tables. I've included its syntax below.

```
db.execSQL( "CREATE TABLE user ( uname VARCHAR, pwd VARCHAR );"
```

E. Insertion

The SQLiteDatabase class's execSQL function allows us to put data into tables. I've included its syntax below.

```
db.execSQL( "INSERT INTO user VALUES('admin','admin')" );
```

F. Fetching/Selection

By using an object of the Cursor class, developer are able to retrieve any database entry. A result set with the cursor pointing to the table will be returned when developer call the raw query function of this class. The data is retrievable by advancing the cursor.[4]

```
Cursor resultSet = database.rawQuery( "Select*from USER", null);  
resultSet.moveToFirst();  
username = resultSet.getString(0); password = resultSet.getString(1);
```

The additional capabilities in the Cursor class that enable us to efficiently obtain the data are displayed in Table No. 1 below.[5]

TABLE I CURSOR CLASS FUNCTIONS THAT ENABLE US TO EFFICIENTLY GET THE DATA

Sr.No.	Techniques and Description
1	getColumnCount() : The total number of columns in the table is returned by this method.
2	getColumnIndex(String columnName) : This function takes the name of the column as input and returns the column's index number.
3	getColumnName(int columnIndex): By providing the column's index, this function retrieves the column name.
4	getColumnNames():The array containing the names of every table column is the result of this procedure.
5	getCount():The total number of rows in the cursor is returned by this procedure.
6	getPosition():The current cursor location in the table is returned by this function.
7	isClosed():If the cursor is closed, this function returns true; if not, it returns false.

III. PROPOSED SQLITE BUILDER SYSTEM:

An open-source Android ORM called SQLiteBuilder re-stores the joy of developing with SQLite databases. It saves developers development time by relieving them of dealing with low-level database needs. An excellent embedded relational database is SQLite. Even still, creating SQL and processing the output of queries are laborious and time-consuming processes. By mapping Java objects to database tables—a process known as ORM, or "object/relational mapping"—SQLiteBuilder re-leases user from these restrictions. In this approach, a straight-forward object-oriented API may be used to save, update,

Figure. 1 High Level Architecture of SQLiteBuilder

remove, and query Java objects. The SQLiteBuilder process's architecture is depicted in Figure No. 1 below. [6][21]

A. Advantages of SQLiteBuilder

The following Some important advantages of SQLiteBuilder library which are helpful for android native developers.

- It reduces time and code of android development it is easy to understand and integrate.[13][14]
- Java classes are mapped to SQLite database tables via SQLiteBuilder. [10][11]
- Offers straightforward APIs for directly saving and re-trieving Java objects to and from SQLite databases.
- User only need to modify the Java Class attributes if there are changes to the database or any table.[14]
- Reduces database access using astute fetching tech-niques.[25][26]
- Offers basic data querying.

- Automatic table creation: The SQLiteBuilder Library gives users the ability to automatically generate database tables.[14][26]

Therefore, it is not necessary to manually build tables in the SQLite database.[6][7]

B. Tools and Software Requirement

This section enlists some of the key software requirements. These requirements are classified into Functional/Technical categories Explicit / Implicit nature. Following table no 2 rep-resent the project hardware and software requirement.[7][27]

1. Operating Environment: SQLiteBuilder works on any android development platform with java or kotlin.
2. Software Interface: The Library Framework will be developed using Java. The Operating system used will be Windows XP Professional OR any other.
3. Hardware Interface: Standard personal PCs are the only hardware interface required. It will be sufficient to create the project on a computer with enough hard disc capacity to accommodate the operating system and enough processing performance to allow it to operate.[8]

TABLE II
REQUIREMENTS OF PROJECT HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE

Hardware Specification.	Software Requirements
SYSTEM: Pentium IV 2.4 GHz	IDE: Android Studio
HARD DISK: 40 GB	Operating System: Windows XP Professional or Any
FLOPPY DRIVE: 1.44 MB	Coding Language: Java, kotlin
RAM: 4 GB	Back-End: SqlLite
	Language: Java

Fig. 2. The Object-Oriented Framework of User Selected Computer Language

IV. OBJECT-RELATIONAL-MAPPED FRAMEWORK:

It would be best to discuss Object-Relational-Mapping as a notion first, before delving into the definition of an Object-Relational-Mapped. Unless user have written a good amount of SQL queries and worked only with non-SQL databases. Typically, they seem somewhat like this: [5]

```
SELECT * FROM users
WHERE email = 'test@test.com'
```

In summary, user are attempting to communicate with database using preferred language rather than SQL. The object-relational mapping enters the picture now. Most people think of a library that uses this method when they say "ORM." For instance, the query from above might now is like this. [5][17][22]

```
var orm = require('generic-orm-library'); var user = orm("users").where({email: 'test@test.com'});
```

The concept of object-relational mapping is the ability to use the object-oriented paradigm of user selected program-ming language, as seen in figure no. 2, to construct both simpler and considerably more complex queries than the one above.[8][9][18]

A. Problem Statement

The Market there are currently lots of ORMs frameworks which provide Object relational mapping functionality includ-ing Hibernate and iBatis which are more mature. However, this framework works with the java based web and desktop application but there is no any available framework which works with android framework. [6] Data reading, updating, and saving are common tasks in the development of Android applications. Occasionally, User could decide to employ an APIS in order to save data on a distant cloud server. But occasionally, storing the data in a SQLite database is the best course of action. For that user need to code far too developed SQLite Queries. This job is very tedious and involves the need to code lots to get data from SQLite data table to Plain Java object. In Android Framework user have to write bilore plate code to do SQLite CRUD operation. This directly impacts on Development time and schedule and code complexity also increases. [9][23]

B. Objective

SQLite Builder has a simple scope for building a robust ORM, which is especially useful for Android developers. SQLiteBuilder simplifies CRUD with basic methods like save(), delete(), select(), and update(). It also automatically builds tables in SQLite databases by mapping POJO classes and provides easy ways for doing one-to-one and one-to-many relationship queries. This ORM can be easily included by including a gradle dependent line in the android Application app. gradle file.[24][32]

C. ORM framework

In essence, the ORM framework and software create objects (as in OOP) that realistically map the tables in a database, much like a city map might.[10][33] After that, these objects would be used by user as a coder to communicate with the database. The primary goal is to prevent programmers from having to write SQL code that is optimized since it is handled by ORM-generated objects. So let's examine a straightforward illustration.[7][11][20] Let's take an example where user have a database with two tables:

1. Customers
2. Items

The ORM framework would then construct equivalent objects (say, clients-object and products-object) that would handle all the database interaction with a little bit of setup on user behalf. In that case, user would need to do is utilize the ORM's customers-Items to add a new client to the database.[1][12][16][34][35] It may be as easy as invoking the objects' "save()" method, for instance:

```
Client = new customersItems ("Stefan","Mischook");  
customers.save();
```

Since the syntax varies between ORM frameworks and languages, the aforementioned is obviously merely pseudocode. The overall idea is how much easier things may be with an ORM framework (no SQL!), and also how much cleaner the code of user application will be.[4][15]

D. Use of ORM framework

By abstracting away the database system, it makes it simple to convert from MySQL to PostgreSQL, or any other flavour user choose. Many sophisticated capabilities, such support for transactions, connection pooling, migrations, seeds, streams, and a host of other delights, are included right out of the box, depending on the ORM. A large number of the queries user create will outperform ones user wrote himself.[6][7][13]

E. Disadvantages of using ORM framework

If user is an expert in SQL, developing his own queries will likely result in higher performance. Every ORM has overhead associated with learning how to utilise it. Setting up an ORM for the first time might be difficult. Knowing what's going on behind the scenes is crucial for developers. user may become a less competent developer in that area of the stack if user use ORMs as a crutch to avoid learning databases and SQL.[8][32]

F. ORM frameworks in Java Objects

Java has several ORM alternatives and persistent frameworks. An ORM service called a persistent framework is used to store and retrieve items into relational databases.[28][29][30][31]

- Enterprise JavaBeans Entity Beans.
- Java Data Objects
- Castor
- Top Link
- Spring DAO
- Hibernate
- And many more

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CONCLUSION

In conclusion, SQLiteBuilder emerges as a transformative ORM tool for Android developers, revolutionizing the way database operations are handled in Android applications. With its interactive query building capabilities, schema management functionalities, and performance optimization techniques, SQLiteBuilder empowers developers to build robust, high-performance applications with unprecedented ease and efficiency. As SQLiteBuilder continues to evolve and gain traction in the Android development community, its potential to shape the future of ORM frameworks and mobile application development practices remains profound.

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